

Appendices of “Gas-phase metallicity gradients in galaxies at $z \sim 6 - 8$ ”

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Appendix A: Additional figures for A2744-YD4

Fig. A.1: NIRSpect PRISM/CLEAR spectra extracted from a circular aperture with radius of $0.15''$ centred at the location of the targets YD6, YD6-[O III]-E, YD4-[O III]-W, and ZD1.

Fig. A.2: NIRSpect PRISM/CLEAR spectra extracted from a circular aperture with radius of $0.15''$ centred at the location of the targets YD1, YD1-E, and s1.

Fig. A.3: Additional maps for A2744-YD4. Highest-resolution continuum map of A2744-YD4 from the original unsmoothed data cube in observed spectral range 1.2–2 μm , where the spatial resolution is the highest (top-left). All the other maps are obtained from the (wavelength-dependent) spatially smoothed data cube, as in Fig. 2 (details in Sect. 2.2). First row: H β (centre) and [O II] (right) integrated fluxes. Second row: [O III]/H β (left) and [O III]/[O II] (right) line flux ratios. Contours mark the 2–3 μm (observed-frame) continuum.

Appendix B: Additional figures for BDF-3299

Fig. B.1: NIRSpect PRISM/CLEAR spectra extracted from a circular aperture with radius of $0.1''$ centred at the location of the targets BDF-3299-b and BDF-3299-c.

Fig. B.2: Additional maps for BDF-3299. As in Fig. 3, the flux maps are obtained from the original data cube, while the line ratio maps from the spatially smoothed data cube (details in Sect. 2.2). Top row: maps of $H\beta$ integrated flux (left), $[O\text{III}]/H\beta$ (centre) and $[O\text{III}]/[O\text{II}]$ (right) line flux ratios.

Appendix C: Additional figures for COSMOS24108

Fig. C.1: NIRSpect PRISM/CLEAR spectra extracted from a circular aperture with radius of $0.15''$ centred at the location of the targets COSMOS24108-b, COSMOS24108-c, COSMOS24108-[OIII]-Ea, and COSMOS24108-[OIII]-Eb.

Fig. C.2: Additional maps for COSMOS24108. As in Fig. 4, the flux maps are obtained from the original data cube, while the line ratio maps from the spatially smoothed data cube (details in Sect. 2.2). Top row: median continuum map in the observed spectral range 3–3.5 μm ($\sim 0.39\text{--}0.46 \mu\text{m}$ rest-frame; left), with the contours of the continuum in the observed spectral range 1–2 μm (same as in Fig. 4, left) superimposed; $H\beta$ (centre-left), $[O II]$ (centre-right), and $H\alpha$ (right) flux maps. Middle row: $[O III]/H\beta$ (left) and $[O III]/[O II]$ (centre-left) line ratio maps.

Fig. C.3: Metallicity gradients for the two minor sources in COSMOS24108, [O III]-Ea and [O III]-Eb (top and mid panels, respectively), and for the main system (bottom panel), when centring the gradient around the peak of the [O III] emission instead of around the continuum peak as in Fig. 6.